

BSE Project
Networks Department
Group ID: BSE18-10
November 2017

**COLLEGE OF COMPUTING &
INFORMATION SCIENCES**
MAKERERE UNIVERSITY

THE NEED FOR A FINAL YEAR PROJECTS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

For

College Of Computing and Informatics Technology

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1. Abstract

Students at the college of computing and Information sciences come up with projects during their final year as a requirement for completion of their program. As a result so many projects come up every year and the supervisors and coordinators have to keep track of all these projects. We have investigated and collected data about how final year projects are conducted and managed currently. The survey aimed at finding challenges supervisors, coordinators as well as students face when conducting final year projects and discovering possible solutions to the challenges. This paper describes our preliminary findings from the survey, recommendations and conclusions are made. The paper also discusses related projects that were done before pointing out their loop holes. We also analyzed the current system and looked at alternatives on how it can be made better.

2. Introduction

Finalists at the college of computing and Information sciences at Makerere University come up with projects every year as a requirement for completion of the program. In groups of four, students come up with ideas to work on that are solving a problem in society. Each group is assigned a supervisor who guides them during this period. Supervisors meet with students on a weekly basis to see whether students are making progress. There is a coordinator who handles general issues from students and ensures that supervisors supervise students.

Coming up with a unique idea to work on is also very cumbersome. Students can solve a problem in sectors like education, health, agriculture etc. They can also choose from previously done projects on condition that they improve the project. The previously done projects can only be accessed from the college library. Students can only read about the projects from the library premises they are not allowed to take out the library material.

Students submit a number of deliverables including Concept Paper, Software Requirements Specification, Software Design Document, and findings report. Supervisors have to review student deliverables either in hardcopy or softcopy and make the necessary changes or approve. It becomes very hectic for supervisors in cases where there are very many student groups to supervise. Each group waits for approval from the supervisor after accomplishing a particular deliverable before moving onto the next task.

There is an online system that is used to register student groups and assign supervisors. In this paper we investigate the challenges with the current system and whether there is need to improve the system. The structure of this paper: The related work section describes the work that has been done before. The methodology section describes the data collection methods used and the population size that was sampled. The results section describes and discusses the findings from the survey and finally recommendations and conclusions are made.

3. Related Work

a. Final Year Projects System:

The Final Year Projects System is a web-based system that provides finalists at the College of Computing and Informatics Technology with the following functionality:

- Registration of final year group members.
- Supervisor assignments from the Coordinator.
- Access to template documents for the different deliverables.
- A list of all Supervisors and Coordinators involved in the program along with their contacts.
- A list of registered groups.

However, the system has a couple of shortcomings, namely:

- Inability of Students to edit / make changes to their group details.
- Does not enable students to upload project deliverables such as reports.
- The system does not allow users to access previous projects (Throws a 404 error).
- Has a non-responsive interface making it difficult to easily interact with on small screen devices.
- Does not enable supervisors to make an assessment of student deliverables and award marks.

b. BIS13-30: Student Academic Project Management Information System

The project intended to address the need for a better projects management system. Aiming at developing an internet based computerized system for managing transactions within the School of Computing and Informatics Technology concerning management and productivity of student academic projects.

The project managed to implement two additional functionalities on top of registration of student groups:

- Awarding of assessment scores for students.
- A discussion forum where Students and Supervisors could comment on general topics.

However, the project simply introduced new functionality without addressing any of the challenges we have discovered with the current System so far. We therefore, intend to address all the shortcomings prior to implementing any additional functionality.

4. Methodology

The research design used for the study of the current system is the survey method. A total of 40 students were sampled; 10 from each of the four programs offered at the college that is, Software Engineering, Information Technology, Computer Science, and Information Systems. This is because only one member from each group interacted with the current system to register the rest of the members. A sample of 10 Supervisors from an approximation of 24 supervisors (6 from each program) was used. Four supervisors from Software Engineering and 2 from the other three programs were interacted with. A sample of 3 coordinators was used since there are four programs and every program has one coordinator. In other words, a sample size of 53 was used.

The main instrument used for the study was a questionnaire. Two questionnaires were used, one for the students and another for both supervisors and coordinators (lecturers) since some supervisors are coordinators. The students' questionnaire consisted of 3 sections; Section A aimed at finding out whether there is need for a new system. Section B aimed at evaluating the current final year project management system's performance and Section C captured the students' demographics.

The lecturers' (supervisors and coordinators) questionnaire consisted of two sections each capturing the need for a new system and evaluating the current final year project management system's performance. Section A was for only Supervisors whereas Section B was for only coordinators.

The respondents were requested to tick the option as applicable to them. The data collected from the 40 students and 13 lecturers (10 supervisors and 3 coordinators) was entered using

epiData from which it was exported to SPSS for analysis. In SPSS, every response was considered from which the more general responses were coded and it is through these codes that frequency tables and bar charts were generated.

5. Results

Based on our data collection and analysis we discuss related challenges faced by students, supervisors and coordinators together with solutions that can be used to tackle these challenges. We summarize our findings in Graph 1, 2, 3 and 4 that are reported in detail in this section

a. Supervisors, students and coordinator perceived challenges concerning the current system.

From Graph 1, the survey shows that supervisors are unable to know individual group progress. This hinders them from keeping track of each group's performance. Supervisors always want to track their assigned groups' progress regarding the final year project from the delivery of concept paper to the final report. Supervisors are also unable to meet students sometimes due to tight schedules. This makes it difficult for them to track the progress of all assigned groups. Supervisors find it hard to know what each member in the group has contributed towards the project which makes assessment difficult. On the other hand some students claim not to be supervised.

From Graph 2, the survey shows that students are unable to upload deliverables using the current system they have to hand in hard copies of their deliverables to the supervisors. The students reported that they lack a discussion forum where they can raise their issues concerning their final year projects. In case of an issue they have to schedule a meeting with their supervisors which is time consuming in cases where an issue needs immediate attention.

The current system doesn't allow changes concerning student group details to be made. When a group wants to make changes to their details they have to communicate with the coordinator for that matter.

Responses from supervisor challenges concerning the current system

Graph 1 showing supervisor perceived challenges with the current system

Responses from student challenges concerning the current system

Graph 2 Showing students' perceived challenges concerning the current system

b. Solutions to the challenges of the current system.

Considering the challenges in Graph 1 and 2, supervisors suggested that there is need to improve the current system as shown in Graph 3. The system should be able to track groups from commencement to completion and creation of individual discussion forum where supervisors can communicate with their assigned groups. From the survey, supervisors also suggested that a system that tracks supervisor student communication to solve the problem of students claiming not to be supervised should be put in place. Supervisors also suggested that a system that enables them to review deliverables online would save a lot of time and money for printing.

From Graph 2, students suggested that: a platform that enables projects to be uploaded, provides general issues discussion forum and tracks student supervisor communication is desirable. Students suggested the provision to edit group details and archive projects to enable ease of access.

Graph 3 showing solutions to the supervisor challenges

Graph 4 showing the solutions to the student challenges

6. Recommendations

The study tells us that supervisors, coordinators and students face a number of challenges when conducting final year projects hence, there is need to improve the current system. A number of solutions were proposed. A platform that enables supervisors to make an assessment of group deliverables, track individual group progress and an individual discussion forum to enable communication between students and supervisors should be created. There is need for a reporting system that enables coordinators to track progress of different groups. A platform that enables students to upload deliverables, discuss issues with supervisors and has an archive of previously done projects needs to be put in place.

7. Conclusion

There is a system in place that is used to support students, supervisors and coordinators when undertaking final year projects. In this paper we point out some of the issues that are faced during this period and remain unsolved. We found that the current system helps in registering groups and allocating supervisors to students but does not sufficiently support the supervisors, coordinators and students at large. The overarching goal is to propose a fully functional system that can be used to track final year projects.